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Disclaimer

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Document information

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2. List of abbreviation

AB	Advisory Board
CAP	Communication & Awareness Plan
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
H2020	Horizon 2020
KPI's	Key performance indicators
MoNS	Municipality of Nea Smyrni
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course ()
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
VCI	Visual Corporate Identity

3. Executive summary

The present document describes the communication and stakeholders' engagement activities implemented for upPE-T during the first 12 months of the project. The objective of the actions implemented up to now has been the communication of the project following the project's Communication and Awareness Plan (CAP) and reaching out to a multi-stakeholder' ecosystem, including academia, researchers, policy makers citizens and industries of the circular economy, bioplastic and food packaging fields.

Deliverable 9.8 will be updated regularly during the project to include new publications, events or other communication activities delivered by the project.

4. Introduction

The communication and stakeholders' engagement activities in the upPE-T project are carried out within Work Package 9 (WP9) "Project Communication and European Citizens Awareness". This WP is led by the Municipality of Nea Smyrni and involves all partners of the project.

Following the development of the Communication and Awareness Plan, a visual identity of the project has been created, which is being used in the various channels developed (social media accounts, website, newsletters, etc.).

In this document we will outline all the communication and stakeholders' engagement activities that are not included in the CAP (deliverable 9.2) and have been implemented during the first year of the project's implementation. These mainly includes publications, newsletters, events and workshops.

5. Participation of partners in events

All consortium partners have worked to raise awareness about project activities and documents within their professional networks. A summary of these events show below.

5.1. Past events

12th February 2021

upPE-Ts coordinator, CETEC, participated in a Science Week event in Murcia, focusing on Women in Science. Students from secondary school had the opportunity to learn about upPE-T and get introduced to the notion of research on the circular economy.

15th March 2021

UNC Umbria honoured the World Consumer Day with a Facebook live broadcast in which they promoted upPE-T and discussed about food waste and sustainable consumption.

REALIZZATO NELL'AMBITO DEL PROGRAMMA GENERALE DI INTERVENTO DELLA REGIONE CON L'UTILIZZO DEI FONDI DEL MINISTERO DELLO SVILUPPO ECONOMICO - RIPARTIZIONE 2020 - INIZIATIVE A VANTAGGIO DEI CONSUMATORI - BANDO REGIONI - DIRIG. AGOSTO 2020 - REGIONE UMBRIA

15.03.2021 Giornata Mondiale dei Consumatori

Diretta Facebook
@consumatoriumbria ore 18.00

L'UNC Umbria onora la giornata dei consumatori lavorando ogni giorno con l'obiettivo di contribuire a difendere i diritti dei consumatori, utenti e cittadini. Grazie a tutti i Nostri Associati e i Nostri volontari attivi!

Parleremo di spreco alimentare
Con il nostro esperto dott. **Albert Verdesse**

E di consumo sostenibile
Con la nostra responsabile progetti ed esperta **Giada Materazzo**

**Be Eco-friendly
Be Responsible**

CONSUMATORI UMBRIA.IT

#INFOONLINE

UNC Umbria
www.consumatoriumbria.it

22 March 2021

The first Advisory Board meeting took place on March 22nd, 2021 in which its nine members gained insight on upPE-T's vision, future plans, opportunities and impact. The upPE-T AB is an independent group composed of external experts that will give guidelines and provide expert advice to the project in order to maximize the impact of the project results.

17 -21 May 2021

CETEC promoted upPE-T in the X International Symposium on Food Technologies in Murcia Spain.

5 June 2021

UNCU celebrated the World's Environment Day with a facebook event.

The World Environment Day was created with the aim of encouraging everyone to become more aware and to take better care of our planet. It is a valuable opportunity to remind ourselves that each of us can do something to be part of the change that the Earth needs, now more than ever.

The theme chosen for 2021 "Restoring Ecosystems" is of crucial importance with the aim of preventing, stopping and reversing the damage inflicted on Earth's ecosystems, thus seeking to move from exploiting nature to healing it.

**GIORNATA
MONDIALE
DELL'AMBIENTE**
5 GIUGNO 2021
ORE 11.30

SEGUITE LA NOSTRA DIRETTA SU FACEBOOK!
INTREVENGONO
- AVV. DAMIANO MARINELLI, PRESIDENTE
UNCU
- GIADA MATERAZZO, RESPONSABILE
EUROPROGETTAZIONE UNCU

www.consumatoriumbria.it

5th June 2021

The municipality of Nea Smurni promoted upPE-T in a community engagement event in Nea Smyrni on the Global Environment day.

ΣΤΥΛ & ΟΜΟΡΦΙΑ | WELL BEING | GOOD LIVING | ΥΓΕΙΑ & ΕΥΕΣΙΑ | ΑΥΤΟΙ

To πανευρωπαϊκό πειραματικό project upPE-T

Μεγάλο ενδιαφέρον παρουσιάζει το πώς η Νέα Σμύρνη πέτυχε να είναι πλέον ένα ευρωπαϊκό hub στον διάλογο της ΕΕ για την κλιματική αλλαγή. Παράλληλα με δεκάδες «πράσινες» δράσεις, ο Δήμος Νέας Σμύρνης, συμμετέχει επίσης σε ένα πανευρωπαϊκό πειραματικό project, το έργο upPE-T. Το πρότζεκτ στοχεύει στη δημιουργία ενός νέου υλικού, ενός αποδομήσιμου βιοπλαστικού το οποίο θα χρησιμοποιείται για την παραγωγή συσκευασιών τροφίμων και ποτών.

«Το πρότζεκτ φιλοδοξεί να συμβάλει στη λύση του προβλήματος με

11th June 2021

MoNS participated in a webinar regarding “The changes that the new Greek bill brings in waste management”. Angela Gaitani presented the innovative technology that H2020 upPE-T project will develop during its four-year implementation period.

17th September 2021

UNC Umbria attended the annual Fashion Design Show organised by the Istituto Italiano Design (IID) at the Sala dei Notari in Perugia. The event focused on circular economy. Participants wore clothes made from materials that were recycled, repaired or reused, with a view to extending their life cycle.

28th September 2021

The Institute for Development and Innovation organized the panel discussion “Young and Green” on 28th September and presented the upPE-T project in Serbia. The event aimed to initiate discussion about green public policies among attendees and panelists. The main topics were:

- Recycling and social inclusion – how recycling and the problem of waste management have an impact on vulnerable groups, with a focus on young people, women, Roma, and senior citizens;
- Environment and the European Union – examples of good practices in the European Union –are they applicable in Serbia;
- Sustainable development goals and local activism – the role of local movements, are they the drivers of major changes in society;
- Corporate social responsibility – how companies contribute to the environment and examples of good practice.

12 October 2021

UNC Umbria organised a seminar to talk about the UPPE-T project in the Sustainable Development Festival 2021 in Italy.

The Sustainable Development Festival is the largest Italian initiative to raise awareness and motivate citizens, the younger generations, businesses, associations and institutions on issues of economic, social and environmental sustainability, to spread the culture of sustainability and to bring about a cultural and political change that will enable Italy to implement the United Nations 2030 Agenda and achieve the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

The Festival has been recognised by the United Nations as an innovative initiative and a unique experience at international level and has twice been classified as a finalist in the SDGs Action Awards.

20 October 2021

uPE-T together with other two H2020 projects organised an **online workshop in upcycling bioplastic of food and drink packaging**. The stakeholders' lists of all three projects have been used in order to promote the project and reach as many people as possible.

The online event was very well received as the following numbers show
Number of registrations from EVENBRITE: 249

Number of confirmations on LinkedIn page: 253

Data from Zoom Report:

- **Number of registrations: 175**
- **Number of attendees: 158**

TOPIC	WEBINAR IDENTIFICATION NUMBER	START TIME	TIMING (MINUTES)	REGISTRATIONS	CANCELLATIONS	ATTENDEES
UPCYCLING BIO-PLASTIC OF F	986 9572 6995	oct. 20, 2021 9:32 a. m.	211	175	0	158

6. Newsletters

The first newsletter published in May 2021 outlined the main key activities of the project.

NEWSLETTER No1

MAY 2021

Welcome to upPE-T

Dear all,

We hereby send you the first issue of the upPE-T newsletter. It contains some updates on recent activities within the consortium and information on what is currently going on with the project.

Details on upPE-T news can always be found on the upPE-T website www.uppet.eu, which was recently launched.

You can also follow us on Twitter @L_upe and LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/uppe-t-project-700591201/>

Enjoy your reading and let us stay in touch. We are very happy to receive any comments you may have at info@uppet.eu

upPE-T Kick-off

The project officially started on November 1st, 2020 and had its Kick-off Meeting (KoM) on 23-24 November 2020. During the two days the members of the consortium had the opportunity to introduce their organization and present their roles within upPE-T.

Scientific Progress

All the partners have made their research plans for year 1, but after only a few experiments at ECO (ECOPLASTICS) and confirmed by CETEC (CENTRO TECNOLÓGICO DEL CALZADO Y DEL PLÁSTICO), we found that the bottle caps we thought contained only polyethylene (PE), are actually blends containing up to 10% of polypropylene (PP) as well. So now we are faced with the decision to change the research plans and include testing future enzyme systems for PP as well, or staying the course and focus only on PE. Work at CETEC and BOKU (UNIVERSITÄT FÜR BODENKULTUR) on the characterization of the different batches of plastic waste (hand sorted by ECO) progresses and increases the understanding of the material. On the PET side in WP2, ECS (ENZYMICALS AG), in collaboration with UG (UNIVERSITÄT GREIFSWALD) has been able to successfully test the first PETase enzymes on a commercially available PET. TAU (Tampere University) and CETEC are finishing up their first round of plastic waste pre-treatments and ECS is ready for determining the effect of those treatments on enzyme activity.

With the recent hiring of a researcher dedicated to WP3, UG can now start their search for a PE degrading enzyme system.

Science Week – 12th February 2021

upPE-Ts coordinator, CETEC, participated in a Science Week event in Murcia, focusing on Women in Science. Students from secondary school had the opportunity to learn about upPE-T and get introduced to the notion of research on the circular economy.

1st Advisory Board meeting – 22nd March 2021

The first Advisory Board meeting took place on March 22nd, 2021 in which its nine members gained insight on upPE-Ts vision, future plans, opportunities and impact. The upPE-TAB is an independent group composed of external experts that will give guidelines and provide expert advice to the project in order to maximize the impact of the project results.

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NEWSLETTER No1

MAY 2021

1st clustering activity – 13th May 2021

A clustering activity workshop took place on 13th May between upPE-T and two other H2020 projects – UPLIFT and PRESERVE – that focus on introducing new technologies in plastic packaging aiming at reducing the adverse impact of plastic to the environment. Partners from the three projects agreed to meet on a monthly basis; organise together a stakeholders' workshop in October; and explore future collaborations in terms of dissemination.

Forthcoming events:

- 2nd Advisory Board meeting on 18th October 2021
- Stakeholders' workshop in October

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7. Press releases

Two press releases have been produced so far. One a month after the kick off of the project and another one in August 2021.

7.1. Press release 24 November 2021

European Commission launches €7.8 million Research and Innovation project on upcycling bio plastics of food and drinks packaging

- The €7.8 million project 'upPE-T' will champion the upcycling of food and drink packaging PE & PET post-consumer wastes to obtain high value products that will be used in the production of biodegradable & recyclable bioplastics (PHBVs) for food & drink packaging manufacturing.
- The upPE-T project will contribute to upcycling up to 60% of food and drink packaging plastic waste by 2030 and develop a viable roadmap to ensure that 60% of the above packaging will be produced from renewable sources by 2030.
- The 4-year project will also increase awareness among EU citizens of products and materials upcycling capacity, bring positive environmental benefits by decreasing 85.6% CO₂ compared to conventional plastics production, contribute to European and international standards and certification schemes.

At present, more than 98% of plastics are produced from non-renewable sources. Some plastics are biobased, however not all are recyclable, reusable, or biodegradable. **Polyethylene (PE) and Polyethylene terephthalate (PET)** are the leading plastics used in food packaging. The progressive substitution of consumer products derived from fossil fuels is crucial to **decarbonise** our society, especially in short shelf-life packaging. In 2019, 19% of food & drink packaging plastic post-consumer waste was still sent to landfill and 39.5% was incinerated for energy recovery in Europe. The sustainable management of such plastic waste has become a very challenging problem for the recycling industry globally. Zero landfilling or incineration is needed to achieve the **circular economy** of plastics. The current alternatives of recycling however have important limitations – (i) mechanical recycling downgrades plastic properties, and (ii) chemical recycling for plastic depolymerisation requires high energy & long reaction times to be effective, consequently only 2% of plastic wastes are chemically recycled.

upPE-T will solve these challenges through an **innovative solution** for the upcycling PE and PET post-consumer packaging wastes by transforming them into a range of biodegradable & recyclable bioplastics (PHBVs) for food & drink packaging manufacturing. The upPE-T project, a Research and Innovation Action (RIA), has received a grant of 7.826.685 € from the European Commission for the [Topic ID: CE-BIOTEC-09-2020](#).

upPE-T will directly contribute to achieve the expected impacts of the topic by: (a) upcycling up to 60% of food & drink packaging plastic wastes (PE & PET) by 2030, (b) highly contribute to increase upgraded waste recycling facilities by introducing

an innovative biocatalytic system in the recycling sector, (iii) establishing a viable roadmap to ensure 60% of food and drinks plastic packaging will be produced from renewable sources, (iv) increase awareness among European citizens of products and materials upcycling capacity, and (v) standardisation & certification facilitating future replicability and widest use and ensure market acceptance.

upPE-T is coordinated by CETEC, Spain and involves a total of 20 European partners from 10 countries including 7 SMEs, a Large Enterprise, 5 Universities, 4 RTOs, a Municipality, a Consumers Organisation (UNC), and a Standard Development Organisation (UNE). The project aims to achieve TRL 6 by the end of its lifetime and involves all the key actors in the supply chain. The project will bring additional positive impacts across Europe in terms of (a) CO₂ decreasing (85.6% compared to conventional plastic production), (b) 0.47Mton PHBV/year produced, (c) an estimated 424,000 tons of plastics not sent to landfilling, and (d) creation of 25 direct and 1500 indirect jobs.

Contact

For questions related to the project, please contact:

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Links:

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Twitter: https://twitter.com/t_uppe

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/uppe-t-project-700591201/>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 953214.

7.2. Press release 21 August 2021

UPLIFT, upPE-T and PRESERVE to hold a joint online workshop on upcycling bio-plastic of food & drink packaging

- The session will count on the participation of three EU-funded initiatives working on bio-based packaging: UPLIFT, upPE-T, and PRESERVE.
- These projects are all working to upcycle food and drinks packaging through different technologies such as biological depolymerisation, enzymatic technologies and enzymes compounding.

Aalborg (Denmark), September 1st. – UPLIFT, upPE-T and, PRESERVE are organising an online joint workshop, *Upcycling bio-plastic of food & drink packaging*, to be held on 20 October 2021. The three initiatives are EU-funded projects under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme. During the session, they will present their work to transform food and drink packaging into new materials or products of better quality or for better environmental value, ensuring that micro-plastics are avoided.

The aim of this event is to build a high-level meeting point for stakeholders across Europe to showcase initiatives and solutions for the food industry packaging that cannot be recycled. The workshop will be divided into three parts: during the first one, the workshop will count on different short talks to frame the European bio-plastic sector, while the second block will showcase the objectives, methodologies, impacts, and expected results of each project. Finally, an open discussion will be conducted regarding the importance of clustering.

Plastics used in food and drink packaging applications are made from a range of polymers and are highly combined with specific additives to meet

each manufacturer's functional and design requirements. This diversity can complicate the recycling process, make it more costly, and affect the quality and value of recycled plastic. Given this, there is a need to develop technological improvements in the sense of better manufacturing and processing practices for these plastic materials to facilitate proper waste management. Developing upcycling technologies will allow sustainable recycling or biological degradation in accordance with existing and novel technologies, standards, and certification schemes.

About UPLIFT

UPLIFT has received €7,5 million funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No. 953073.

Led by Aalborg University, UPLIFT is formed by Forschungszentrum Julich, Austrian Centre of Industrial Biotechnology, Technical University of Denmark, Lunds Universitet, TECNARO, Bio-M, Bio Base Europe Pilot Plant, Leibniz-Institut fuer Naturstoff-Forschung und Infektionsbiologie - Hans Knoell Institut, Plastics Technology Centre AIMPLAS, University College Dublin, Bioplastech, Sustainable Innovations, RWTH Aachen and I/S Vestforbrænding

UPLIFT CONTACT

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About upPE-T

upPE-T has received €7.8 million funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 953214.

Led by CETEC Plastic Technology Centre(Spain), upPE-T involves a total of 20 European partners from 10 countries -Enzymicals AG, Eco Plastics, Footwear Technology Centre of La Rioja (CTCR), Tecnoalimenti S.C.P.A, Institute for development and innovation, Digiotech, Unione Nazionale Consumatori Umbria, Municipality of Nea Smyrni, Durukan Confectionery INC, The Spanish Association for Standardization (UNE), Cetec Biotechnology, BIO-MI Ltd., Villani Salumi S.P.A, Moses Productos, Universität für Bodenkultur Wien, Tampere University, Lappeenranta-Lahti University of Technology, University of Alicante, and University of Greifswald

upPE-T CONTACT

Fuensanta Monzó, Project Coordinator, CETEC
info@uppet.eu

About PRESERVE

Preserve has received €7,9 million funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 952983.

Led by IRIS Technology Solutions, PRESERVE has 26 partners: Fraunhofer IVV, Fachhochschule Albstadt-Sigmaringen, Centexbel, AImplas, Fraunhofer IVV, ITENE, Next Technology Tecnotessile, Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna, Biopolis, Planet Bioplastics, Bostik, Carbiolice, Südpack, Graphic Packaging International, Sibio, Beiersdorf, OWS, Pla.to, Romei, DenimX, Silon, Kneia, Crowdhelix, European Bioplastics, Danone, Ferrero.

PRESERVE CONTACT

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8. Stakeholders' engagement

As it was mentioned earlier in this report, several of the communication activities that have taken place so far aim to reach and engage stakeholders.

Also, as it is outlined in the CAP (D9.2) one of the initial and most important tasks for stakeholders' engagement is their identification and mapping. To this end the project's consortium with the lead of MoNS initiated a series of project's meetings, which resulted in a list of stakeholders.

Meetings with partners

The meeting with partners took place in the following dates:

- 21/12/2020
- 25/01/2021
- 1/3/2021
- 20/4/2021
- 6/7 2021
- 7/9/2021
- 5/10 2021

The main topic of the first meetings was the information that upPE-T should keep in the stakeholders' list. MoNS circulated a template in which partners gave their feedback. The final form that was agreed to be completed regarding the stakeholders' list included the following information:

- ✓ Stakeholders' details
 - Name of organisation
 - Sector
 - Contact Person
 - Email address
 - Website
 - Country

- ✓ What kind of expertise will the stakeholder bring to Up-PET
- ✓ Stakeholder's interest
- ✓ Stakeholder's attitude
- ✓ Stakeholder's influence on...
- ✓ Level of influence
- ✓ Power/ Impact on project outcomes
- ✓ Geographical impact
- ✓ Notes

Once the content of the form was decided, partners were asked to engage with potential stakeholders. Each partner was agreed to suggest at least five organisations for the stakeholders' list.

Once partners contacted and had the stakeholders' agreement, they sent the stakeholders' information to MoNS in the agreed table.

This resulted in a list of more than 100 stakeholders from the industry, academia, politics and the third sector from across Europe, who can be contacted through emails, newsletters, etc.

Furthermore, partners agreed to develop a form on the project's website, in which organisations can fill in their contact details and become part of the project's stakeholders list, get invited to events and generally get involved in the project's developments. This form shows below.

We would like to keep in touch to let you know about the project's developments and invite you to our events, which could be a great opportunity to exchange with experts involved in the transition towards a circular economy from all over Europe.

If you think that you and your organisation can contribute to the project's aim, we would welcome your involvement.

First name *	<input type="text"/>
Last name *	<input type="text"/>
Email address *	<input type="text"/>
Website	<input type="text"/>
Organization *	<input type="text"/>
Sector *	<input type="text"/>
Country *	<input type="text"/>
Your subscription *	<input type="checkbox"/> By subscribing to this list, you accept to receive information about events, news and/or newsletters about H2020 upPE-T 1
Security Check	<input type="checkbox"/> I'm not a robot
	<input type="button" value="Submit"/>

The personal data collected will only be used to send you news about upPE-T. You can change your mind at any time by clicking the "update your preferences" or "unsubscribe" link in the footer of any email you receive from us. We will treat your information with respect. If you think

Advisory Board

Part of the stakeholders' engagement is also the development of an Advisory Board (AB). The purpose of the AB is to help the project gain new insights and advice to solve problems that are arising or to explore new opportunities by stimulating robust, high-quality conversations. Membership of the AB is on a voluntary basis without financial compensation.

The AB consists of industry, academic, policy making and businesses representatives. Candidates to the AB were nominated in the project proposal stage by project partners and approved by the Executive Board, while new members joined after the successful approval of the project.

All members were selected for their knowledge and experience to the upPE-T areas of implementation, so that they can actively contribute to the project goals and desired outcomes.

Members of the Advisory Board come from the following organisations and sectors as outlined in the table below.

SECTOR	ASSOCIATION/ORGANIZATION NAME	COUNTRY
Biotechnology	Industrial Biotechnology Innovation Centre (IBioIC)	United Kingdom
Policy makers	EURADA	Spain
SSH AND GENDER ASPECTS	DROSOTALIDA Social Enterprise	Greece
	Innovative Education Center	Austria
	PRIMAFLOR	Spain
Packaging	SARTEN PACKAGING	Turkey
Environmental	ACLIMA	Spain
Biotechnology	ITALBIOTEC	Italy
Circular economy	FUNDACIONPLASTICSENSE	Spain

The AB will provide strategic direction, guide quality improvement, and assess the project's effectiveness.

So far one introductory meeting was held in March 2021, whereas another one is planned for later in the year 2021.

Stakeholders as well as Advisory Board members were invited in the clustering online workshop which was organized with other two sister H2020 projects on 20th October 2021.

9. Conclusion

This Deliverable has presented the communication and stakeholders' engagement activities developed so far.

This document will be updated and reviewed regularly and will be reported in the progress reports of the project.